

Inscriptions from Kadwaha, Dist. Guna (M.P.)

Arvind Kumar Singh

The village of Kadwaha is situated 19 km. away to the north of Esagarha in the Guna District of Madhya Pradesh. It is known for a large Hindu Monastery and more than a dozen temples. The solid and robust monastery reveals a well laid out plan and impressive elevation and built like a fortress with surrounding walls and battlements. Likewise, the splendid temples of Kadwaha are well planned and managed, for which the place is regarded as the Khajuraho of the former Gwalior State.¹ Various stone slabs and architectural members of the monastery and temples bear inscriptions. During our visit to the site I have noticed more than forty inscriptions. Of these, the earliest one is of 10th century A.D. while the latest one belongs to 16th century A.D. Most of them are now in fragmentary condition and it became difficult to know their purport and even to read some of them. The preserved portions consist mainly information about the name and activities of the rulers, nobles, Śaiva āchāryas, pilgrims, scribes and massons.

The history of region is conspicuous, unique and fascinating. The early history of Kadwaha goes back to the pre-historic times. Some stone tools have been discovered from the area.² Further, here we do not find the socio-economic stratification and political features as seen in northern India and elsewhere from the Vedic times down to the Guptas and even later. The livelihood of forest tribes was animal husbandary and forest product. The depiction of

memorial stones and their inscriptions indicate that cattle raids were common and the practice continued even during Gupta period when a Mahattara (Chief) losing life in a *goharaṇa* episode.³ The evidence of Tunda-Bhadaka khoh (Distt. Shivapuri)⁴ evince that natural rock shelters served as the habitat of people like the bhadakana-s who were Bhagavatas and who take keen delight in decorating their cave habitat in the 2nd century B.C. with painting, offering an insight into the contemporary animal life, the life of cave dwellers, hunting gathering techniques, material culture, family and social life, mythology and spiritual life. The site is very rich from viewpoint of hives which in a way indicate the use of forest produce, besides, their food habits and liking for the honey. It seems that modifications were introduced in the āṭavikas communal organisation with the advents of the Chaulukya and Pratihars in the region. During the same time, artisans and traders seem dominant in the region, virtually running the administration through a council composed of the sārthavāha, śreshṭhis, the chief of gardeners, the chief of oilmen, etc.⁵ Kin groups among the tribes may have been closely linked but Varna and Caste were not appropriately formed as it is obvious from the instances of a Brahman of a doubtful gotra (Vāsala gotra and bheraṇḍa anvaya)⁶, of a kshatriya as a tiller⁷ and Vaiśya as rulers. It is further supplemented by the information occurs in the travel account of Yuwan Chwang about Vaiśya being the rulers of Maheshwarapura (same as Gwalior) and

presence of a belt of Vaiśya rulers from Gwalior to Ujjain. In absence of a centralised political authority and regular ruling dynasties till the 9th century A.D. tribal chiefdoms exercised political control and there is a distinct presence of bhaṭas like Nagarabhaṭa, Vaillabhaṭa⁸, Undabhaṭa⁹ Gobhaṭa and Durbhaṭa whose position graduated from mercenary warrior to that of Koṭṭapāla, rājā, bhūpa, ṛipati, mahāsāmantādhipati to mahārājādhirāja. Here we notice a queer pattern now in the polity underlining absence of the overlord and assertion of primary by the bhaṭas who sometimes proclaimed themselves as Mahārājādhirāja even as they invoked their overlord.¹⁰ The known king of the Chaulukya or Sulki family who ruled over the Kadwaha region till the last quarter of the 10th century A.D. are Avantivarman, Simhavarman, Sadhanva, Avanivarman, Narasimha and Kesarin. Soon thereafter, Hariraja, advanced on Kadwaha. Other rulers of this dynasty were Bhimadeva, Ranapala, Vatsaraja, Svarnapala, Kirtipala, Abhayapala, Govindaraja, Rajaraja, Viraraja and Jaitravarman. The inscriptions of some of these kings have been found at kadwaha,¹¹ which denotes that the place was included in their dominion. The rulers of Delhi Sultunat and Malwa invaded the area at different times and occupied it. For sometime it was under the sway of Narwar rulers.

A. A fragmentary stone inscription from Kadwaha (10th century A.D.)¹², consisting twenty nine lines, mention Purandara as the first person of a lineage of the Saivacharya who came from Malwa at the invitation of king Avantivarman of Chaulukya family and chose Aranipada (Ronod Dist., Shivapuri) for his penance. The name of his disciple is now lost but he is described as 'bhuvanāśryapaṇḍita'. King Gobhaṭa came with his army of elephants¹³ while after a sudden death of a person (probably the ruler of the place) whose name is not preserved, the sage was filled with compassion, and then like Tripurāntaka conquered the whole army of the foes by means of a bow and arrow acquired by his own miraculous power.¹⁴ He was succeeded by another Śaiva sage, whose name is lost, and a

paramount ruler (Nṛipa-Chakravartin) called Hariraja came to see the sage. This āchārya gave *dikshā* to Hariraja and at the end of the said *dikshā* ceremony, the king offered some rutting elephants as *gurudakshinā* who refused to take them, but being repeatedly requested by the king he was inclined to receive some villages instead. The name of a mighty ruler, Durbhaṭa, is find mention but his father name is not preserved now. The inscription understudy deviate on some points like it refers Purandara as the first saint in the Mattamayura (Kadwaha) line while other inscriptions in the Chedi region mention to him as a descendent rather than founder. According to the Ranod inscription,¹⁵ Purandara (same as Mattāmayūranātha) was fifth in descent from Kadambaguhādhivāsī. The movement seems to have started with the Śavite saint Guhāvāsī (kadambaguhāvāsī, i.e. the inhabitant of Kadambaguhā) possibly at Kadwaha in A.D. 675. A regular monastery was later built here by Purandara who also established a monastery at Aranipada. The disciple of Chūḍāśiva, named Hṛidayaśiva went to Maihar, invited by Lakshmanaraja (A.D. 946-973). However, Mattamayura line continued even after Hṛidayaśiva¹⁶ as a Pratihara ruler Hariraja (c.A.D. 984) got *Dikshā* from a disciple of Dharmāśiva. The entreaty of rulers to their temporal authority, pontiffs assistance to rulers in battle, their titles like *adhipati*, *pāla* and *nāth* confirms that the pontiffs proclaiming their own supermacy and asserting their role as protectors of people. In view of Misra the Śaiva potiffs were in a demand because they may have served the purpose of the state in its war efforts and it may explain the location of the *maṭhas* in the peripheral region of the state which were vulnerable to external aggression.¹⁷

B. The inscription of V.S. 1366 thursday, Magha sudi 11 is engraved in 7 lines on a slab in the pavement of Śiva temple in the Garhi (Pl. 151) It records that the sage (*tapodhana*) Bhūteśwara, worshipped the Mahāliṅga of Mūlāyatana when the world was harassed by the Mlechhas. Also records that he did

serve penance after the Mlechhas had committed sins (*pātakas*) nineteen times and he made a new Jalādhāra, when the previous one was broken by the Mlechhas. The writers of the record were Pandita Vatsaraja and Pandita Kshemdhara.¹⁸ The language of the inscription is Sanskrit, which is written in Nāgarī characters.

1. सिद्धि : ऊँ नमः शिवाय । संवत् 1366 माघ सुदि 11 गुरौ महाराजाधिराज
2. श्री पातसाहि अलावदीन विजयराज्ये समस्त भूमण्डले म्लेच्छैक
3. पद्भुते सतिमहालिंगं मूलायतनं तपोधनेन भूतेस्वरेणाच्चितः
4. एकोनविंशतिशंख्याके वर्तमाने पातके सति महात्मना
5. भूतेस्वरेणोग्रं तपोकारि जलाधारेम्लेच्छैर्भग्नेसतितेन
6. व्योवृत्पनौतनं चक्रे ।
7. पं वत्सराज पं क्षेमधराम्यां लिखितं ।

C. On a door-jamb of the Śiva temple in Garhi an inscription is engraved in 34 line. The language of the inscription is Sanskrit and script is Nāgarī. Due to the rough engraving it is legible and intelligible only in parts. It consists 5 verses and seems to be a praśastī. The first verse invokes a blessing of Śiva on the king Jayamtavarmana. Verse 2 mention the reign of Gopāla and Kshitiipāla and further praises Jayamtavarmana. Verse 5 records the date in words.¹⁹ In line 21 Jayantavarman is spelt as Jaitravarma.

1. ऊँ नमः शिवायो विजितरि
2. पुपुरः परांविभूर्तिंदयदाधिकं
3. दिलसन्कालानि मिश्रण संभव
4. त्रभवत । जयंतवर्मन वदनुष्कष
5. गुणः शिवः शिवाय ॥ 1 वणक्षरा
6. पति वंशमौक्तिकमणिर्मानिग
7. पृथीपतिः क्षीरभिरनिमिस अवी
8. सुभमणिः सद्दृत रक्षामणिः । गो
9. पाल क्षितिपाल राज्ये कमलास्नी

10. धवनषिंधामणिजीयादष जयंत
11. वर्मणाकृतां सक्षात्रचूडामणिः । 2
12. सोयंजीयाकुयंतस्त्रिभुवनभवन
13. स्यंसानंद कीर्त्तिमूर्त्तिश्चुरम्भाविम
14. थीकृतमदनं च गुनगयत्वंगलत्तम
15. यष्णौर्यस्य प्रसस्याः ब्रमथषरिष्व
16. देः संत्गरेथीतभगंविस्तारेणप्रस
17. स्तिरिपुधरणिस्वनां भातपीठं
18. पर्यंत/3 सतांदुद्धंचवीर कौतु
19. कवसाकखिलूद्वाशुसिधनि
20. ग्नः प्याततले कलानिधिरां
21. मूश्री जैत्रवर्माधिः । तं न
22. अडिड मुस्थ भारचितवीष
23. ड्गधकृत्तं यथावग्रकांदारा
24. काम्रनंदतलिमेवस्त श्री म
25. नालिंमग्नेः ॥4 अंगास्नी
26. कविशीददीधितिषदि
27. संवत्सरे सीम्मतिमासे
28. फाल्गुन केशितहेगति
29. रौवारै च वविस्सत । जि
30. त्वाढय कमूप्तरिणा सारु
31. संनांद्रा चलंद्रं तलेति
32. जाष्वि श्री जयंतवर्मम
33. ति ठ त्रिजोपि साक्षी
34. कृतः ॥5

D. An inscription of the year (V.S.) 1450, thursday Vaiśākha sudi is engraved on south Kakshāsana in the mandapa of Ṭoteśvara Mahādeva temple (Pl. 152). It records some gift to the Brahmana Bhagohara belonging to Gautam gotra by Pandita Rāmadāsa

who was the son of Pandita Dhanaudeva and grandson of Mujāladeva. Rāmadāsa is described as a devotee of śiva.²⁰

1. ॐ नमस्तिः ॥ श्वर्गर्थहरं सोयदामेसिप वनस्त्वं कुतवहस्त्नमां पस्त्वं व्योम
2. आधरणि सत निमिधिपाधरिच्छिन्नाये वंभूयि परिणतां विस्त्रतु
3. सेनु विद्ययत्र नवुयुगिह निथत्वन्न भवितः ॥ व संवत् 1450
4. वैसाष सुदि गुरौदिने ॥ भागोहर ब्राह्मणायो गौतम गोत्राय
5. - यदोस्त्रायिन ॥ पंडित श्रीमुजालदेव तस्य पुत्र पंडित श्री धनौदेव
6. तस्य पुत्र पंडित श्रीरामदासदेवः ॥ शिवभक्तः ॥ शुभभवत् ॥

Other three inscriptions of the same slab are of one line but not much clear. A tentative reading of these inscriptions are as follows :

- D. 1. सुश्रीधुसुतस्याम्रसरु शिवभक्तु ॥ ॥ सं 1380
- D. 2. — अमरसीव शिवभक्त ॥
- D. 3. — तुरु भिरवन त्रिभुवस्ति.

E. Inscription of the year (V.S.) 1512 Sunday, Māgha sudi 11 and Śaka year 1377 is engraved in 12 lines on a stone slab in the *garbhagriha* of Ṭoṭeśvara Mahādeva temple (Pl. 153). It begins with a obeisance to Gaṇapati, mention the reign of Mahārājādhirāja Sri Sultān Mahamud Śāh. The writer of the inscription was Mahipāla, son of ṭha (ṭhakkura) Sri Thirapāla and *sūtradhāra* was Gagumata. Some of the letters in lines 8 to 11 are not clear and only a tentative reading is given here.

1. ॐ ॥ सिधि गणपति प्रसादात् ॥ आद्यब्रम्हान विश्रणितिजल
2. गगन । नास्ति ब्रम्हांडगंडं ॥ भ्यर्गाद्यानवैनागा। ग्रहगण
3. रिषथ्यो ॥ नास्ति नथ्यत्रमाला ॥ चंद्रादित्यो न वहति
4. वह्नि सरित ॥ नास्ति कलिनेजीव ॥ तत्रे कौपिस्वयं भू
5. त्रिजुगजुगपति ॥ तातमास्रिष्टि कर्ता ॥ संवत् 1512

6. वर्षे ॥ माघ सुदि 11 रवौ दिने ॥ अथ विक्रमादित्यराजे साके
7. 1377 महाराजाधिराज श्री सुलितान महमुद साहिणलवी
8. राज्ये वेदेठीदेस्यो दोलविषामघष्टमानै ॥ सात्री श्रीनरोन्नतस्य
9. पुत्रपौत्री श्री धगार्माकिस चुलवंसतीया डादुगवेत्रत तपं
10. तस्यगम पुत्र सहकुणे वसागश्री सुत्रधरद ॥ तस्य पुत्र रावतं
11. रतनपाल तत्यक्षसम्बनाक्रत्तम—लिषिता ठ श्री
12. थिरपाल पुत्र महिपाल ॥ सुभमस्त ॥ सूत्रधारि गगूमति

F. A twelve lines inscription is found in the interior wall of the Jaina temple (Pl. 154). Though it is in a good state of preservation but at some places lime blur make difficult to read a few letters. The present inscription is a praśasti, consists of eight verses in Sanskrit language. It begins with the praise of Chāhaḍa and describe the achievements of Kumārāpāla. This eulogy was written by Naithā.

1. — चाहडक्षणिभुजोगरिन्नः प्रतापस्वशोपीहर्चरित्रारिः । प्रजाप्रमोदामश
2. भूपश्वरः स्वयंशद्रस्यं च तमोनिहंता ॥ 1 तस्यपुत्रो महावाहुर्मालनो भवतती । मुं
3. द—कमंडूलब्राल्लूणीत् ॥ 2 सूभ्यश्चथतिघूर्णमालदाधिः षापुतहे अ
4. क्षतांश्चरित्रोदलनाय कोनदलनय शाकंभरी शोभयात्येकग्रामपुरः प्रभुर्चल्लडि
5. धितिर्भामदेवीपतेः क्षात्रं वर्णम्भिनुप्रनुः रंधूर्निर्णनां जिह्वासहस्रेण चेत् ॥ 3 ॥ त
6. स्यावभूत्साहसमम्लचीरोवीराग्रेणीवीरारोतूगर्हः । शशांक चूडांहसहपपत्र सौरम्ये
7. विजा चल चंचरी कः ॥ 4 ॥ दभक्तिनिष्ठः समरेजविष्टो विवेक कष्या सुजनेषु हृष्टरिषू
8. विपुष्टोप्यदितः सुमूर्तिः कुमारपालोभुवितेव्वकीर्तिः ॥ 5 ॥ तेनैषानिमिता चा
9. पी भुवन चूडापादनी ॥ हंसभारैर्चत्येभिर्यापाश्वानाकारयत्यपि ॥ 6 वित ---मरं

10. शिम्त्सस्करौ सावासशसुरनिम्लयाथरिधुतिस्यतीयावट—
मूपसयाकुटी विने
11. मपकीर्त्तितावत् ॥ 7 ॥ गौडान तसमग्राभूवमुरधुरः
पुदिदक्षणष्टो । दक्षिणा
12. — कृपयाश्च त नैथा लिखिता कृतिः ॥ 8 ॥ संवत्
1351 मार्गवदि 11 शुक्रे

G. The present inscription is inscribed on a Satī pillar depicting the scene of horse rider and soldier with sword besides traditional scenes like a hand, sun, moon, Śiva linga and Upāsaka on the upper part. Inscription in the lower part bears the date both in Vikrama and Śaka era. Its object is to record the name of Chamāra Idau's son Shamhau, an inhabitant of Kadwaha which was under Nalpur (Narwar) district, who was probably died in a battle and Ratanā, the daughter of Jushpau of Lalitapur become Satī. This Kanhāmātā was made by brother Haripāla with the help of Sūtradhāra Daija.

1. सिद्धम् ॥ संवत् 1451 वर्षे शा—
2. के 1316 ॥ मार्गशिर्ष शुदि 15
3. रवौ दिने ॥ अद्येह श्री गोगिमी
4. पुरे महाराजधिराज श्री सु—
5. रताण महमद गजणी राज्ये त—
6. स्मिनुकाले वर्द्धमाने नलपुर
7. देसे कदवाहे वास्तव्य । चमार इदौ
8. पुत्र षम्हौ ललितपुर जूषौ
9. चमार तजू पुत्री रतना सह—
10. गमनं कृत्वा । तस्य भाई
11. हरिपाल कन्हामाता करापितं ॥
12. सुतहा (धा) रि दैज

H. Some small and incomplete inscription are noticed on the fragmentary stone slabs now preserved in a room of the monestery and on the other stones of the Garhi.

H.1. On a loose stone slab in monestery in two lines mentions the name of viramubhaṭṭa²¹ and other inscription of year 1172 and 1550.

- (1) I. विरमुभट्ट
- II. वर्षे
- (2) I. गातिपितां ठ श्री—
- II. षंवत् 1550 व—
- (3) I. लिसडं असीगपतं सप्ररेद्यट्ट
- II. न्युसदिनासुद्यथ
- III. सावत् 1172 वर्षे

H.2. A loose stone in Hindu monastery in 2 lines record Sarnvat year and name of the writer which reads Gaja.²²

1. लिषितं ॥ ठ श्रीगजां संव—
2. 1527 वर्षे श्रावण

H. 3. Another loose stone bear the inscription of year 1551, Pausha sudi and record the name of writer Venī Achhūtipūrī.²³

1. सावत् 1551
2. वार्षे पौषा सुदि लिषि—
3. तं वेनी अछूतिपूरी

H. 4. An inscription of year 1552 is engraved on a loose stone in 3 lines which is not clear now.

1. सवात् 1552
2. लिषिमस्ते अदा
3. ——— थुरा

H.5. A loose stone in monastery in 6 lines bear the name of writer and date.

1. भट संवत् —
2. जेठ सुदी 5
3. श्रीरतनदो—ठीजरदौस्य

(क) 1. सिधि । संवत् 15—

- (क) 1. संवत् 1-59 वर्षे पुष — 8 मंगलवार भाष्टेष्वाकेर
2. सोय राहामाता सीध सावग्नोः मनसुट
3. — परधना

K. Of the two fragmentary inscription from kadwaha, one bear the data of 1569 while only 152 of the other inscription in now preserved.

- (क) 1. संवत् 1569 वर्षे
2. सदैस्तुघत
3. —तलव्यातती
4. —सुरा
5. —दिभ

- (ख) 1. त-णितावे हो असू
2. घ— 152

L. Sati stone and the temples of Anghora Diwan also bear some inscriptions. A preliminary reading of these inscriptions are given here.

- (क) 1. संवत् 1786 वर्षे
2. सावन वदी 14 पु
3. यपरप्तो सती भई
4. राछसी घरई सुपुछ
5. वसभस
6. —
7. रीछदीतपुरास
8. तीसदा
(ख) 1. त्रीणजी
2. त्रालला श्री
3. मणत जीगी
4. माती झनयत
5. 186 वर्षे
(ग) 1. 1595—सुदि 4
2. —इरषूस
(घ) रषभदेव

M. The Vishnu group of temples also bear some inscriptions and masson marks. Of them, one inscription is engraved on a floor stone of the temple in one line and records the date as saṁvat 1134 Thursday, Aṣvina sudi 2 and a name ending with deva.²⁷

— — ग - देव । सं 1134 अस्विन सुदि 2 गुरौ

N. Some more names also find mention in the inscriptions of Kadwaha. On the foot of an image unearthed in debris of Garhi one line inscription records the name of Bhaṭṭāraka Śrī Vakrasādhu in character of about 10th century A.D.²⁸

On the sill of window on the second storey of Garhi, one line records name of the Manjudeva, 2 devotee of Śiva and another Brahmana in character of about 16th century A.D.²⁹

A loose stone slab of monastery bears the date as saṁvat 1138 Monday vadi 15 in 4 lines inscription.³⁰ An inscription of year 1234 begins with a obeisance to Gaṇapati and refers to Gosurālaya.³¹ Inscription of the year 1384 Māgha sudi 10, contains a verse in Upagiti metre, possibly refers to a night scene in Vasānta. The writer was Honideva.³² A seven lines Sati inscription records the construction of a Sati monument of Rāvat Kusal's wife in the reign of Dilāwar Khān.³³ The name of the writer Ratansiha, son of Thirapāla occurs in a Garhi inscription of year 1466.³⁴ Another Ratan, son of Dhanarāja finds mention in the inscription of year 1475.³⁵ Likewise, another inscription of year 1479 register the name of Saipāla who was the son of Thirapāla.³⁶ The members of a Pachapriya Brahmana family, namely Haridāsa, his son Harihari and harihari's son astrologer Gangdās, besides Vaidana, son of Kāyastha Mohansiha of Ranthambhor is recorded in a ten lines inscription of year 1487 Thursday, Jeshtha Vadi 7.³⁷ The names of Ronapāla, his son Jairāja and Arjuna are legible in a inscription of year 1499 on a stone slab in Garhi.³⁸ Inscriptions dated in the year 1504 records the reign of Sultan Mahmud Khilji and other names like Śrī Gopāladeva,

son of Śrī Mahipāla, the writer Sāranga son of Paigu, Ratansimhadeva.³⁹

Inscriptions suggest that sometimes whole of the family was engaged in writing work. Thirapāla's three sons namely Ratansih (in V.S. 1466), Saipāla (in V.S. 1479) and Mahipāla (in V.S. 1512) were engaged in writing the inscriptions. It also indicates the hereditary nature of profession in which a person used to learn profession since the childhood. The profession of writing was elevated as it attracted some Panditas while some others bear the title like ṭhakkur. The name of artisans and masson marks help to know about the

author of monastery and temples. The complete study and interpretation of the inscriptions may help to better understand the various aspects of the history of the region.

Acknowledgement

For the photographs my thanks are due to the Head, Ancient History, Culture and Archaeology, Jiwaji University, Gwalior and the Director, American Institute of Indian Studies, Ramnagar, Varanasi. My thanks are due to Dr. S.K. Dwivedi for his kind suggestion.

REFERENCES

1. *Annual Report of the Archaeological Department Gwalior State (GAR) for Vikram Samvat 1984, Year 1927-28, Gwalior, p. 7.*
2. Sharma, R.K. 1974 *Madhya Pradesh Ke Puratattva ka Sandarbha Grantha*, Madhya Pradesh Hindi Granth Academy, Bhopal, p. 107.
3. Singh, A.K. 1994-95 'Some Hero Stones of Gwalior and their Inscriptions,' *Prāgdhārā*, No.5, p.139.
4. Singh, A.K. 1997-98 'Tunda Bhadaka Rock Painting and Inscriptions : Some Interpretations,' *Prāgdhārā*, No. 8, pp. 213-220.
5. For detail see, Misra, R.N. 1989-91 'The Saivite Monasteries, Pontiffs and Patronage in Central India,' *Journal of the Asiatic Society of Bombay*, Vol. 64-66, pp. 108-123; 1997 'Pontiffs' empowerment in central Indian Savite Monachism, *Ibid.*, Vol. 72, pp. 72-86;
6. Sircar, D.C. (*EI*, XXX, p. 146) says that Vasala gotra is not known from old works on gotra and pravara.
7. Dwivedi, H.N., (V.S. 2004), *Gwalior Rajya Ke Abhilekha*, inscription nos. 8-9 : क्षत्रिय देववर्मासुत मेम्मक वाहित क्षेत्र।
8. Hultzsch, E., 'The two Inscriptions of the Vaillabhattachasvamin temple at Gwalior, *EI*, I, pp. 154-162 : Vaillabhattacha had been chief of the boundaries (maryādādadhurya) while Alla had been the guarding of the fort (koṭṭapāla) of Gopadri. The name of Vaillabhattacha is also mentioned in a Memorial stone Inscription, Singh, 1994-95, *op. cit.*, p. 141.
9. F. Kielhorn, 'Siyadoni Stone Inscription, *EI*, I, p. 169 : Undabhata is described as Mahapratihara, Samadhigatas- eshamahasabda, and Mahasamantadhipati. He is also

- mentioned with the date (V.S.) 960 in Terahi Memorial Stone Inscription.
10. Misra, R.N., *op. cit.*
 11. A fragmentary stone inscription from Kadwaha in 32 lines, in the character of about 11th century A.D., records after four benedictory verses the kings of a Pratihara family and some persons of a Brahman family. Verses 5 to 19 describe Ranapala, Vatsaraja, Svarnapala, Kirtiraja and his brother Uttama. The name of Lohapala and Govinda are only preserved now who belonged to a Brahman Talarashtra race or family. It also mentions the names of Ballaladeva and Jaittravarman in the inscription of border which was added in about 13th century, *GAR for 1996*, pp. 45-46, No. 31.
 12. Mirashi, V.V. and A.M. Shastri, 'A Fragmentary Stone Inscription from Kadwaha, *EI*, XXXVII, pp. 117-124.
 13. तत्रा जगमोन्मद सिन्धुराणां वलेन भूपः किल गोभटाख्यः, *Ibid.*, p. 123, line 12.
 14. तस्यावगम्य स कथां करुणाविमुक्तवा पः क्षणं तदनु कोपविपाटलाक्षः ।
जलदस्सलक्ष्मीः ॥ अथ प्रभावागतकार्मुकेण वाणेश्च दोप्तः धरावृषांकः ।
आस्वलीलस्त्रिपुरांतकस्य, *Ibid.*, p. 122.
 15. Kielhorn, F. 'A stone Inscription from Ranod,' *EI*, I, pp. 351-361.
 16. A Fragmentary stone inscription from Kadwaha, consisting 24 lines, gives the genealogy of a line of Saiva ascetics but the name of only Isvara Siva (1.11) occurs in the preserved portion. He is eulogised as a heap of penance. It also mention the planting of garden (1.7) and of the construction of certain mansions (probably monastic building). The name of Siddhesvara and other three Brahmanas namely Gangadhara, Vamana and Sripala Misra find mentions. Sripala Misra was the poet and Mangalaraja was the writer of the inscription. Bhima Bhupa mentioned in the line 16 may possibly be Pratihara Bhimadeva. *GAR for 1996*, pp. 44-45, No.30.
 17. Misra, R.N., *op. cit.*
 18. *Archaeological Survey of India Annual Report on Indian Epigraphy (ARIE) for 1975-76*, p. 97, C. 4131; *GAR for 1997*, pp. 52-53, 4.
 19. In a view verse 5 records the date in words having conventional numerical values, which when interpreted, may yield the year 1626 which is obviously referable to the Vikrama Samvat era. *GAR*, 1996, pp. 46-47, 32; While the name of a Jaittravarman find mention in the inscription of 13th century A.D. (see 11 above).
 20. *GAR for 1984*, pp. 36-37, No. 66; *ARIE for 1961-62*, p. 153, c. 1440.
 21. *GAR for 1996*, p. 40, No. 4; *ARIE for 1975-76*, p. 96, c. 4126.
 22. Other reading suggests the name as Gaya, *GAR for 1996*, p. 41, 9; *ARIE for 1970-71*, p. 105, C. 3033.
 23. *ARIE for 1975-76*, p. 97, C4128.
 24. In a view the dates samvat 84 and 735 engraved separately seem to be irregular *GAR for 1996*, p. 40, No. 2; *ARIE for 1975-76*, p. 96, C 4124.
 25. *GAR for 1984*, pp. 36-37, No. 63 refers that the name of a Gumasta at paraganas Ranod and Kadwaha find mention. In other reading gumasta named are Samhikhan and two

- Malikas Sahana and Khudil and Kadaraha
Prāgdhārā ARIE for 1961, p. 154, c 1447.
26. The date is suggested as 1580 and the title of
Kumarapala as Ro *ARIE for 1961-62*, p.
154, c 1450.
27. *GAR for 1984*, pp. 36-37, No. 72, *ARIE for*
1961-62, p. 155. C 1454.
28. *GAR for 1996*, p. 43, No. 29; *ARIE for 1975-*
76, p.98, c 4135.
29. *ARIE for 1961-62*, p. 153, c1432.
30. *GAR for 1996*, p. 41, No. 10.
31. *ARIE for 1975-76*, p. 98, c 4134.
32. *GAR for 1996*, p. 40, No. 3; *ARIE for 1975-76*,
p. 96, c. 4125.
33. *GAR for 1984*, pp.34-35, No. 58. refers the
inscription with the date V.S. 146?
34. *GAR for 1996*, p.43, No.25; *ARIE for 1961-62*,
p.159, c, 1433.
35. *GAR for 1984*, pp.34-35, No. 55; *ARIE for*
1961-62, p. 153, c. 1436.
36. *GAR for 1996*, p. 43, No. 24.
37. *GAR for 1984*, pp. 34-35, No. 51, for 1996, p.
43, No. 26.
38. *GAR for 1984*, pp. 34-35, No. 50.
39. *GAR for 1984*, pp. 34-35, Nos. 49, 52-53; for
1996, pp. 41-43, Nos. 14, 24, 27; *ARIE for*
1961-62, p. 153, c 1437; for 1970-71,
p. 105, c 3030.

Dr. Arvind Kumar Singh

School of Studies in
Ancient Indian History
Culture and Archaeology
Jiwaji University
Gwalior (M.P.), INDIA